

ADJUSTMENT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF LOCOMOTOR IMPAIRED AND HEARING IMPAIRED SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to find out the Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired students in Sikkim. The sample of the study comprised of 100 differently abled school students. Out of which 48 students had Hearing impairment and 52 students had Locomotor impairment. Descriptive survey method was applied. Results of this study revealed a significant difference in the home adjustment and school adjustment of Hearing Impaired students and Locomotor Impaired students.

Keywords : Adjustment, Academic Achievement, Hearing Impaired students, Locomotor Impaired students

Introduction :

Adjustment refers to the outcome of the individual's attempts to deal with the stress and meet his needs, also his efforts to maintain harmonious relationship with the environment (Coleman & Rasoff, 1963). Academic achievement is an index of success of students' performance, teachers' efforts and significance of curriculum and educational objectives. It is the most desirable outcome of school life (Upadhyay and Raino, 2017).

Inclusive education is understood by Lipsky and Gartner (1996) as equitable opportunities for all learners to receive effective educational services, with supplementary aids and support, in age-appropriate classes in their neighbourhoods to prepare them for contributing lives as full members of society. Inclusive Education (IE) is a new approach towards educating the children with disability and learning difficulties with that of normal ones within the same roof. It brings all students together in one classroom and community, regardless of their strengths or weaknesses in any area, and seeks to maximize the potential of all students (Singh, 2016).

In an Inclusive setup efforts are applied from the management, administration and the teachers' side for the

success of inclusion but it takes time for the differently abled students to get adjusted. When the social and psychological needs of the differently abled students are not gratified they may develop adjustment problems (Ranjan, 2014). Student's adjustment level in the school determines his/her academic achievement.

Some studies have been conducted on Adjustment and Academic Achievement of differently abled students.

Banoo, Vaida, Nadeem and Bhat (2017) reported that there was a significant difference in the school and social adjustment of hearing impaired students and locomotor impaired students. A research conducted by Aqil and Rai (2018) on adjustment of college students with loco-motor disability revealed that there was a significant difference in the adjustment of students with locomotor disability with regard to the variable of gender. Altarawneh (2018) revealed a significant difference in the adjustment of students with disabilities with regard to gender. Jha (2018) found that disabled student's had low academic achievement. No special teacher and professional rehabilitation workers were found in these schools. Tettey, Cobbina and Hamenoo (2017) also stated that institutional barriers such as effective instructional procedures, availability of facilities, teaching, reading

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learning materials, and curricular contents posed challenges to the academic performance of students with hearing impairment

Objective Of The Study :

1. To find out the difference between Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students in their Home adjustment
2. To find out the difference between Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students in their Social adjustment
3. To find out the difference between Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students in their Emotional adjustment
4. To find out the difference between Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students in their School adjustment
5. To find out the difference in the Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students

Hypotheses :

- H0₁ There is no significant difference in the Home adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.
- H0₂ There is no significant difference in the Social adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.
- H0₃ There is no significant difference in the Emotional adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor

Impaired school students.

H0₄ There is no significant difference in the School adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

H0₅ There is no significant difference in the Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

Methodology :

In the present study descriptive survey method was used. The sample for the study comprised of 100 differently abled students studying in various schools of Sikkim. Out of which 48 students had Hearing impairment and 52 students had Locomotor impairment. Stratified random sampling technique was employed to collect the sample. HOSOCES Adjustment Inventory developed by N.A Nadeem was used as the tool for the study. For data on Academic Achievement student's grade cards for two academic sessions were collected from both Government and Private schools located in all districts of Sikkim. The statistical techniques used for the study comprised of percentage, mean, standard deviation and t-test.

Analysis And Interpretation Of Data :

Objective 1: To find out the difference in the Home adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

H0₁ There is no significant difference in the Home adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

Table 1: Home Adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students. (df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)					
IMPAIRMENT	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Hearing	48	8.22	5.71	4.146	Significant at 0.05 level
Locomotor	52	3.807	1.980		

It is evident from Table 1 that there is significant difference in the home adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Objective 2: To find out the difference in the Social

adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

H0₂ There is no significant difference in the Social adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

Table 2: Social Adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students. (df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)					
IMPAIRMENT	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Hearing	48	9.083	4.093	0.723	Not significant at 0.05 level
Locomotor	52	9.346	3.216		

It is evident from Table 2 that there is no significant difference in the social adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective 3: To find out the difference in the Emotional

adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

H0₃ There is no significant difference in the Emotional adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

Table 3: Emotional Adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students. (df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)

IMPAIRMENT	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Hearing	48	10.18	3.74	0.0044	Not significant at 0.05 level
Locomotor	52	8.28	2.59		

It is evident from Table 3 that there is no significant difference in the emotional adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Since the mean value of Hearing Impaired school students is higher than that of the Locomotor Impaired school students. This implies that the Hearing

Impaired school students are emotionally better adjusted than the Locomotor Impaired school students.

Objective 4: To find out the difference in the School adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

H0₄ There is no significant difference in the School adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

Table 4: School Adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students. (df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)

IMPAIRMENT	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Hearing	48	14.70	5.073	4.006	Significant at 0.05 level
Locomotor	52	7.67	5.024		

It is evident from Table 4 that there is significant difference in the school adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Objective 5: To find out the difference in the Academic

Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students

H0₅ There is no significant difference in the Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

Table 5: Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students. (df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)

IMPAIRMENT	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Hearing	48	30.45	12.11	0.55	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Locomotor	52	32.01	14.41		

It is evident from Table 5 that there is no significant difference in the Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Findings And Discussion :

The study found that there is no significant

difference in the social adjustment and emotional adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students. It was also revealed that there is a significant difference in the home adjustment and school adjustment of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students. This finding is in consonant with the findings of Banoo, Vaida, Nadeem and Bhat (2017) who reported that there was a significant

difference in the school adjustment of Hearing Impaired students and Locomotor Impaired students. Further the study indicated that there is no significant difference in the Academic Achievement of Hearing Impaired and Locomotor Impaired school students.

Conclusion :

Inclusion involves keeping special education students in general education classrooms and bringing the support services to the child, rather than bringing the child to the support services. One of the components of successful inclusion is the degree to which the student with a disability feels a part of the general education classroom. The feeling of belonging positively affects the student's speed of adjustment to the larger classroom and general level of achievement. Fostering positive social relationships between students with disabilities and their peers requires the preparation of nondisabled peers in the classroom so that they understand the needs of their new classmates (National Association of Special Education Teachers Report # 7, 2004). Inclusive education requires a group effort. The success of Inclusive education depends on how well the teaching and non teaching staff, students, families, administrators and policy makers cooperate, reflect, share resources, responsibilities, skills and advocate for the student's welfare.

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